

SPIRITUAL AND PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF SPEAKING TEACHING

Safin Dmitry Shamilevich

Teacher of Samarkand state institute foreign languages
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8107165>

Annotation: This article discusses how to teach the language skills and the spiritual and educational foundation.

Key words : lexical, grammatical, pronunciation, expression, speaking skills, speaking ability, speech material

Foreign language teaching in the methodology to speak teach " orally to the speech teach ", " thought oral statement to do to teach ", " to communicate like teaching ". terms with is expressed . Chet language of teaching primary purpose students free to communicate to teach by doing defined present in the circumstances to speak to teach foreign language of the lesson the most important practical stage as is being considered .

Speaking is something the idea expression reach in order to certain in the language lexical , grammatical and pronunciation events from applying consists of First think , then say , it is said for nothing not ". In the "Think " section thought appear to be , in " Soyla " . while him speech , action intuition analyzer through " statement " sides _ mean is caught . The first is language of the material they are used lexical , grammatical , pronunciation skills is called , the second is an opinion to say aspect is speaking qualification name qualification with is conducted . To talk to teach the idea written statement do (to write teach) , others speech listening understand (speech perception reach and understanding) , Reading to understand like speech activity types with organic in dependence organize will be done . Because to pronunciation , new lexicon , grammar to the material without teaching , listening to understand , to speak , to think written statement to do to teach possible not _ Communicative method supporters to speak to teach head goal as before pushing _ only to speak in the process pronunciation , grammar to the material , listening and by reading to understand , the idea written statement to do to teach proposal with they are coming out . Theirs according to foreign language as a system not a means of communication as learning main is a task . This that we did not reject the idea without traditional and communicative of the methods use of students language material appropriation to levels according to differential or complex organization to do to the goal according to will be Because each how the method in choosing the first in line of students memory , attention , ability , mastery level like to adjectives attention is directed .

So by doing to speak in teaching traditional and communicative a complex of methods use to the goal is appropriate . Foreign language of means using the idea oral statement to do to teach much complicated process is considered and in it one road three speech program perform demand will be : language material choice , perception to do and understand it _ speech in the process apply _ From this come came out without the first in line of students linguistic competence (language material choose forming potential , _ ie lexical and

grammatical skills formation practical result gives _ To talk to teach sentences memory , perception to do , certain one speech in the case of thought tell get , error from doing do not smell like row psychology factors too depends. Language tools using the idea statement reach one so much difficult will pass Because this in process one of time in itself two kinds of speech program to perform right comes : one to thinking about , that is thought conduct aspect if , the second language units is to apply . From him except dialog (pair speech) and monologue (solo speech) in features sharp differences felt stands _ Couple in speech shortened units of the tongue all to the events applicable will be This of speech from freedom proof gives _ Couple of speech basis different replicas organize is enough Replicas to speak exclamation point and answer from the sentences consists of will be Replicas from the merger dialogic unity harvest will be done . Of them question-answer , question-question , message- question , message-message, message additional message, sentence urge - message, speech prompt-question , like elements couple is often found in speech . Couple of speech main features the following : 1) inseparable two of the replica speech to the situation suitable arrival _ 2) couplet - only question and answer not different _ of replicas exchange are the results ; 3) dialogic ellipses in unity and of abbreviations own in place application ; 4) of the interlocutor replica partner's with content connection _ Alone speech too to himself special characters with differ : 1) relative continuity judgment pushes , suddenly more than sentence is said , therefore , opinion connected without statement will be done ; 2) content consistency observable , expressed ideas support sentences by means of little by little by developing will go ; 3) feedback known level completion speech in samples is expressed .

To talk in teaching initially in students couple speech qualifications is formed and asta - slowness with alone speech qualifications to form will be passed . To talk to teach every _ in the form of too the following methodology and psychological requirements compliance is done : 1. Speech of the material information in character to be provide _ 2. Students speech activities stimulating method, method and of means efficient use _ 3. To speak in teaching each one of the student individual features in consideration received without differential approach . 4. Language materials speech situations through communication processes input _ 5. Speech of the subject novelty , interest provide _ 6. Speech to the forms in teaching of sentences content and meaning main attention focus _ 7. To speak in teaching group speech activities organize to do of possibilities use _ 8. To speak in teaching from new pedagogical technologies use (internet, design teaching , debate , debate , discussion) 9. Students to the conversation introduction formation of potential (competence) .

To talk in teaching each one of the student active study activities providing , free thought tell will receive positive psychological environment create important _ This point of view from the point of view students wrong _ logic contrary , opposite _ _ thoughts not to be condemned , but to be supported and this to thoughts others relationship notice measures to see it is necessary Error thought stated student this through thinking , active study to the activity entered , own his opinion foreign in the language express get it means _ Such communication in the process students themselves criticism it's a mistake thought from reporting not to worry is taught . Interlocutors , groups organized conversations in the process mutually friendly indiscriminately help _ cooperation , mutual each other _ understanding happened gives _ Couple speech in teaching in students to the conversation enter get potential shaping too important To the conversation introduction potential

different speech situations what how to speak to speak , sentences how to each other connect , interlocutor his opinion intuitive understanding , to him confirmation , confirmation , denial in forms answer to give ways to teach through is formed .

To the conversation introduction potential shaping a lot in terms of of students the following speaking skills take over to their foreheads depends on : 1. Interlocutor attention to himself focus formulas by learning get _ 2. Own mind face, hand actions with (mimicry and gesture) expression ways by learning get _ 3. Necessary words not found in the rest paraphrase , synonym, antonym, Actions , gestures and another tools through explanation ways by learning get _ 4. Talk structure simplifying to speak by learning get _ Errors in this road from putting do not smell 5. Speaking incorrectly when he put him to correct from the interlocutor please from doing not to be ashamed . 6. Necessary being otherwise , conversation topic by changing to send methods to know Next in years publication being done Method in the literature of students to speak qualifications in formation them attention , memory , thinking acceptability activator emotional effect of means use about thoughts is being reported .

Russian Methodist scientists E.P. Kumarova and E. N. Tregubovalar to speak in teaching the following emotional effect from the factors to use recommendation they do : 1. Communication in the process student to the brain cognitive (to thinking exclamatory), emotional (emotional intuition stimulating), psychomotor (mental to action causing) effect doer tool and of methods use _ 2. Communication in the process in the class, in the group of students fear feelings , mistake by doing from putting shame , sharp spiritual situations eliminate to do measures to see 3. Communication the topic is humorous, nice mood in content to be provide _ 4. Communication in the process of students hearing , seeing , feeling , perception to do complex to analyzers effect doer tool and of methods use _ 5. Communication in the process students between sincere , impartial friendly relationships and study cooperation to be installed reach _ The student's all complex positive to the senses or negative effect only as specified his thinking ability activates . Such cases human intellectual capabilities one how many increased to leave proved . From this come came out without students cheering , laughing , cheering to speak , to listen and by reading to understand to teach psychological -methodical system create task come coming out So by doing ntq to the activity Linguistic, psychological , methodological in teaching of factors to commonality reach foreign the language to teach placed practical , educational , educational and developing goals efficient done increase provides .

Literature:

- 1.Пассов Е.И. Коммуникативный метод обучения иноязычному говорению- М: 1985.
- 2.Пассов Е.И. Стояновский А.М. Ситуация речевого общения как методическая категория. ИЯШ. 1989,№2.
- 3.Цетлин В.С. Реальные ситуации общения на уроке французского языка. ИЯШ, 2000,№3,с.24.
- 4.Абдумурод Кўчибоев. Француз тили ўқитиш методикаси.марузалар матни Сам ДЧТИ нашриёти – Самарқанд: 2005,83-б.
- 5.Жамол Жалолов.Чет тили ўқитиш методикаси Тошкент “Ўқитувчи” нашриёти,1996.

